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Third Year Management Report

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Abstract

This document connects the deliverables submitted in year three to the project objectives. It reports the work performed during this final year within the work packages, summarizes achievements and risks. Finally, we conclude by analysing feedback we received from the project's External Advisory Board.

Keywords

Deliverables, achievements, milestones, risks, mid-term review

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Contributing Partners

Abbreviation	Company name
BI	BARKHAUSEN INSTITUT
AUS	AUSTRALO
EAB	ERICSSON
IFAG	INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES AG
NXP	NXP SEMICONDUCTORS
IHP	IHP MICROELECTRONICS
NOK	NOKIA NETWORKS GERMANY
NNF	NOKIA NETWORKS FRANCE
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN

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Executive Summary

This document marks the completion of the last year of COREnext, concluding the project as a whole. It connects the deliverables submitted in year three to the project objectives as defined in the project proposal. We also report the work performed within the work packages that resulted in these deliverables and summarize major achievements and managed risks. The report concludes with a statement from the project's Advisory Board made following the presentation of the project demonstrators showcasing COREnext results.

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Acronyms and Definitions

ASIP	Application-specific instruction set processor
AFSIW	Air filled substrate integrated waveguide
AXI	Advanced extensible interface
DU	Distributed unit
eWLB	Embedded Wafer Level Ball Grid Array
FPGA	Field-programmable gate array
ISA	Instruction set architecture
LDPC	Low density parity check
O-RAN	Open radio access network
PE	Processing element
PHY	Physical layer
PMF	Polymer Microwave Fiber
RAN	Radio access network
RISC	Reduced instruction set computing
RVV	RISC-V vector extension
TLS	Transport-layer security
VRF	Vector register file
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

COREnext focuses on trustworthiness and efficiency improvements for future 6G networks. In the three years of project runtime, we intend to address two key technical gaps:

- COREnext offers efficient and scalable hardware accelerators, leveraging programmable components with domain-specific RISC-V extensions and reconfigurable processing on FPGA. The compute fabric relies on power-efficient interconnects to meet sustainability targets while also serving the increasing throughput and latency needs of applications.
- COREnext develops a trustworthy-by-design architecture, which protects user privacy and platform integrity, while supporting 6G compute demands in edge servers, base stations, and client-side devices.

In year three, the main technical deliverable flow (see Figure 1) connects to the final deliverables of year two. Year two ended with D3.2 finalizing the trustworthy disaggregated computing architecture, after receiving feedback from the component development in work packages 4 (digital) and 5 (analogue), respectively. In addition, D2.3 conducted an analysis of trustworthiness requirements and their implementation. Starting from this architectural and trustworthiness viewpoints, year three was focused on validation and impact generation. Development of the technical components to their final level concludes in both work package 4 (digital) and work package 5 (analogue). The final component results were reported in D4.4 for digital components, D5.2 for trustworthy analogue components, and D5.3 for analogue efficiency components.

These final components are then handed off to be validated in work package 6, with validation demonstrators motivated by their fit into the overall project architecture. While the broad scope of the project does not allow full integration of every component into one demonstrator, our goal is to have multiple demonstrators fully covering the component innovations needed to realize the COREnext architecture described in D3.2. Key performance indicators aggregated in D3.2 will be used to validate the project demonstrators, which are reported in D6.1. Lastly, the project delivers D7.1, an industry roadmap that positions the COREnext results in a wider context. Using future use cases from D2.3 as well as expertise within the consortium and from outside experts, D7.1 identifies gaps and needs beyond the scope of COREnext and describes research targets that should inspire future research projects.

Figure 1: Main COREnext deliverable flow in year three

Additionally, in this period, the project produced 7 scientific publications (see Table 1 below for details) and the consortium members attended and presented COREnext-related content in 9 events including EuCNC 2025, EuroSys & ASPLOS 2025, OSDI & ATC 2025, DAC 2025, DATE 2025, European Microwave Week 2025, and Embedded World 2025.

In summary, this third-year management report outlines the progress towards the project's objectives as documented in deliverables and scientific publications. We summarize the work performed by the beneficiaries within the work packages, including major achievements and managed risks. This document concludes with an analysis of the feedback we received from the project's Advisory Board.

2 Progress Towards Project Objectives

In this section, we connect the progress highlighted in the deliverables and publications to the project objectives as outlined in the proposal and grant agreement. As the project work is organized towards the goals of efficiency and trustworthiness, for both digital and analogue components of the RAN, we can structure the objectives as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Structure of project objectives

Objective 1: Computing architecture for sustainable and trustworthy B5G/6G processing

This objective targets an open, multi-vendor, and multi-tenant RAN architecture. **In year three**, and as anticipated in COREnext project plan, no further work directly on the architecture was expected. Consequently, the associated WP3 has ended already in year two. However, components have been validated in WP6 using KPIs defined by the architecture. In addition, scientific publications with architectural impact were published.

Objective 2: Infrastructure and signal processing capabilities for B5G/6G disaggregated virtualized network

This objective zooms in on efficiency of the digital processing. Novel accelerator designs for RAN functions are being developed to improve energy efficiency compared to off-the-shelf hardware. **In year three**, these components were finalized within WP4, and results were reported in D4.4. The components were then handed off for validation to WP6, where they become part of architecture-motivated demonstrators. KPIs have been matched against architectural requirements and D6.1 evaluates how the project delivers on its overall goals.

Objective 3: Enablers for trustworthiness, GDPR-by-design computation-communication platform

Focusing on the trustworthiness side of digital processing, this objective expects the design and development of hardware trust mechanisms for secure isolation in the presence of untrusted hardware components. **In year three**, work on the M³ platform and its trusted execution environments, as well as FPGA virtualization for multi-tenancy, and scalable IoT management have been finalized in WP4, and results were reported in D4.4. The components were then handed off for validation to WP6, where they become part of architecture-motivated demonstrators. KPIs

have been matched against architectural requirements and D6.1 evaluates how the project delivers on its overall goals.

Objective 4: Analogue components and ML algorithms enabling trustworthy 6G connectivity

Identifying devices over a wireless connection by their analogue fingerprint is the target of this objective. Such identification already at the wireless interface improves connection integrity and thus trustworthiness at this first line of defence. **In year three**, the radio fingerprinting was finalized within WP5, with results reported in D5.2. Like the objectives above, the achievements were handed off to WP6 for validation through demonstrators, with results reported in D6.1.

Objective 5: Analogue HW solution enabling ultra-high speed data interconnect for B5G/6G infrastructures

This objective contributes to system efficiency from the analogue components side. A millimetre-wave data interconnect using plastic fibres as waveguides is designed, targeting a competitive energy consumption of less than 1pJ/bit. **In year three**, the interconnect was finalized within WP5, with results reported in D5.3. Like the objectives above, the results were handed off to WP6 for validation through demonstrators, with results reported in D6.1.

Objective 6: Strategic roadmap for disaggregated communication-computing platform involving European microelectronics and telecommunications players

Within this objective, an integrated overall roadmap is expected to offer a gap analysis between industrial practice and research results by COREnext and beyond. **In year three**, external expert consultations were used to refine the initial version of the deliverable D7.1 generated in year two. In addition, the project presented its demonstrators at EuCNC to engage in discussions with the research community as well as representatives from industry.

The deliverables and the scientific publications are manifestations of the progress towards the project objectives as seen in Table 1:

Artifact	O1	O2	O3	O4	O5	O6
Deliverables						
D4.4: Final Report on Trustworthy and Efficient Digital Components	.	✓	✓			
D5.2: Refined Concepts for Trustworthy Radio Links Through HW Imperfections and Localisation			.	✓		
D5.3: Design of Sub-THz Transceiver Circuits and H-Band Plastic Waveguide					✓	
D6.1: Lab Validation Results	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	.
D7.1: Computing-Communication-Sensing Platform Integration Roadmap	✓
D8.2: COREnext Impact Report	✓
Scientific Publications						
Distrusting cores by separating computation from isolation	✓	.	✓			
An Architecture for Shrinking the TCB of TEEs on Heterogeneous Systems	✓	✓	✓			
Development of a Universal FPGA-Based Coprocessor for 5G NR and WLAN LDPC Coding		✓				
Separate but Together: Integrating Remote Attestation Into TLS	✓		✓			
Fast End-to-End Simulation and Exploration of Many-RISCV-Core Baseband Transceivers for Software-Defined Radio-Access Networks		✓				
D-Band Channel Modeling in Data Centers and Industrial Environments				✓		
Ultra-broadband Frequency Multiplier (x8) Chain in 90nm SiGe BiCMOS Technology at H-band					✓	

Table 1: Deliverables and publications in relation to project objectives

3 Work Performed in Year Three

This section summarizes all work performed in year three towards the project objectives and deliverables. We group outcomes by work package, with Figure 3 giving an overview of the project until now. As this is the final year of the project, all work packages are concluding.

Figure 3: Project implementation timeline

3.1 WPI: Management and Coordination

The management and coordination work package is responsible for ensuring overall scientific and technical excellence in the project. It coordinates between project bodies and manages the reporting to the European Commission. Apart from continued regular online meetings, the project partners met twice in person during the third year:

- for a plenary meeting in February 2025 in Frankfurt (Oder) and
- at EuCNC 2025 in Poznan to showcase the project demonstrators and outreach to key stakeholders.

Achieved Outcomes

After receiving feedback from the mid-term review in 2024, project partners met for a plenary meeting in Frankfurt (Oder) at the site of partner IHP to discuss the feedback and how to address it in the remainder of the project. In year 3, the management and coordination efforts of WP1 focused on a successful hand-off of project components from WP4 (Digital) and WP5 (Analog) to WP6 and the development of the demonstrators. Meeting schedules were restructured to adapt to the change in coordination needs. The management team also prepares the project results for presentation at the final review meeting with the commission and external reviewers.

The core team uses the predetermined project milestones to structure and guide the overall work and to set a clear work focus. All milestones in year three were achieved on time:

- Month 33: Component development finalized
- Month 36: Validation in the lab finalized

After component development concluded, the project presented its lab demonstrators to the advisory board to receive feedback on the impact and dissemination activities of the project. A statement regarding this feedback is part of this deliverable.

Risk Assessment

None of the foreseen risks have manifested. A challenge was posed by the fact that the consortium agreement mandated a stringent NDA for members of the advisory board. Negotiations and corresponding restructuring of the board delayed the planned board meeting up until early November 2025. All deliverables marked for public dissemination are now available on the project website and on Zenodo.

Deviations From Project Proposal

Deliverable D5.3 got delayed because of a personal situation of a key author. We arranged for a later submission date with our project officer, which we could meet.

3.2 WP2: Trustworthiness and Use Cases Requirements

Work package 2 completed in the second year of the project. Therefore, no work was conducted in the third year.

3.3 WP3: Trustworthy Disaggregated Computing Architecture

	2023				2024				2025			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
T3.1 Disaggregated B5G/6G scenarios and data flows												
T3.2 Component advancement on the terminal												
T3.3 Component advancement on the base station												
T3.4 Component advancement on the edge cloud												
T3.5 End-to-end architecture supporting identified data flows												

D3.1 M4 ✓
D3.2 M5

Work package 3 completed in the second year of the project. Therefore, no work was conducted in the third year.

3.4 WP4: Digital Components

	2023				2024				2025			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
T4.1 RISC-V based processor cores as computing building blocks												
T4.2 Heterogeneous acceleration for 6G capabilities												
T4.3 Trustworthy authorisation, orchestration, and interfacing												
T4.4 Virtualisation features for compute resource deployment												

D4.1 ✓
D4.2 D4.3 M6
D4.4 M7

During the third year, WP4 activities focused on the following work package objectives:

- WPO 4.1: Increase in computing capabilities to meet B5G/6G performance and efficiency demands.
- WPO 4.2: Virtualisation features for disaggregation, multi-tenancy, and multi-vendor requirements.
- WPO 4.3: Deeply embedded trustworthiness primitives for enhanced privacy and integrity.

WP4 supported the achievement of milestone 7 in month 33 with the conclusion of the component development and the successful delivery of **D4.4: Final report on trustworthy and efficient digital components**.

The following sections summarize the achieved results, outputs, outcomes, and assessed risks for the different components developed in WP4 and link the work to the different tasks listed above.

Achieved Outcomes

WP4 progressed well in all four tasks defined for the work package, namely:

- Task 4.1: RISC-V based processor cores as computing building blocks
- Task 4.2: Heterogeneous acceleration for 6G processing capabilities
- Task 4.3: Trustworthy authorization, orchestration, and interfacing
- Task 4.4: Virtualisation features for compute resource deployment

The work on these four tasks is aligned to two main research directions, which we present below.

Acceleration of the RAN

For **Task 4.1: RISC-V based processor cores as computing building blocks**, after including mixed-precision floating point extensions in the processing elements of the many-core TeraPool cluster we proceeded in mapping a complete application, namely the data-processing part of the PUSCH on the cluster. We extracted post place and route power, performance and area metrics for the application and we compared our results with state-of-the-art programmable processors for the lower-PHY. We further explored the addition of RISC-V vector (RVV) extensions to the processing elements of TeraPool. The results on mapping the lower-PHY workloads to a many-core cluster supporting RVV extensions is left to future work.

As part of task **T4.1** CYB researched modifications of current computer architecture enabling self-protecting data such that security properties can be realised without extensive dependencies on system level software.

For tasks **T4.1** and **T4.2: Heterogeneous acceleration for 6G processing capabilities**, TUD investigated the utilization of vector processors based on the proposed RISC-V vector extension (RVV) for communications signal processing in general and the High-PHY processing of the O-RAN Distributed Unit (DU) in particular. The aim is to build an efficient programmable accelerator that lies between general-purpose processors and fixed-function accelerators, or application-specific instruction set processors (ASIPs) on the performance-flexibility trade-off curve. The initial investigation is presented in deliverable D4.1. TUD have identified the vector register file (VRF) as a bottleneck in contemporary vector processors. When the vector processor is running with high utilization, the VRF must support many concurrent accesses. While banking reduces some of the access conflicts, state-of-the-art static bank layout leave room for improvement. TUD has analysed the bank conflicts and proposed dynamic bank layouts to either improve performance or save area-expensive operand queues with loss of performance. A paper on this topic was published in an ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimization.

As part of **Task 4.2**, a high-throughput LDPC accelerator was successfully developed by IHP to address the demanding error-correction requirements of 5G and 6G systems. The design employed a fully unrolled hardware architecture that eliminated control-flow overhead, resulting in deterministic and ultra-low decoding latency. To increase flexibility, the implementation supported dynamic code-rate adaptation in the range of 0.5 to 0.846 through selective check-node deactivation. Laid out and simulated in 28 nm FD-SOI technology, the prototype achieved up to 1 Tb/s coded throughput with only minor BER degradation compared to a floating-point reference.

Furthermore, in **Task 4.1 and 4.2**, IHP designed and evaluated an AI-driven MAC scheduling accelerator named AIMOS to enhance real-time radio resource allocation. The scheduler applied machine learning to replace traditional rule-based algorithms, enabling adaptive and QoS-aware

scheduling decisions. Implemented on a custom NVDLA-based hardware accelerator, AIMOS generated complete scheduling outcomes within less than 50 μ s, fully satisfying 5G timing constraints. Simulation and evaluation using the 5G-LENA framework confirmed improved overall throughput and fairness compared to conventional methods such as Round Robin and Proportional Fair scheduling.

After evaluating several PULP-based RISC-V platforms together with ETHZ as part of **Task 4.1**, IHP selected the Cheshire platform as the foundation for our RISC-V-based processing system. Cheshire proved ideal for the objectives, as it combines a CVA6 core for control-plane tasks with integrated accelerators for data-plane processing, making it well suited for future heterogeneous designs. We familiarized ourselves with the platform and the CVA6 cores and successfully integrated the NVDLA accelerator via system buses and memory-mapped registers. This setup now serves as the hardware platform on which the AIMOS scheduler operates.

Virtualization and Trustworthiness

In **Task 4.3: Trustworthy authorisation, orchestration, and interfacing**, solutions towards FPGA virtualization are being developed. Current FPGA virtualization solutions do not address authentication, even less so in a multi-tenant context. We have developed a hardware trusted execution environment (HWTEE) to enable user multi-tenancy inside FPGA logic for data processing acceleration. Sharing logical resources among multiple users involves securing data being processed by each user with the help of cryptographic algorithms. The proposed HWTEE is a hardware communication wrapper which first initiates cryptographic keys exchange between the tenancies and the FPGA logic. Then, the HWTEE ensures encryption/decryption by minimizing processing time as much as possible. Two demos have been shown. The first was presented at the first COREnext plenary meeting of the year 2025 in the context of a collaborative work with ETH Zürich. The second demo, which has been proposed at EuCNC 2025, was an adaptation of the first demo applied to FPGA acceleration processing in Cloud computing.

In **Task 4.4: Virtualization features for compute resource deployment**, experimental setups analogue to production base stations were brought up. The setups feature 3 architecture candidates offered by silicon industrials for the implementation of future generations of mobile networks. The different architectures were brought up progressively along the first half of this year. The Open Air Interface software stack had to be improved to leverage the capabilities of the candidate architectures in this period. Especially the integration of the O-RAN Accelerator Abstraction Layer – which enables the virtualization of some specialized compute resource – was completed. The second half of the year was dedicated to studying the behaviour of the candidate architectures under workloads analogue to a production setup. The knowledge obtained from setting up and operating this infrastructure was disseminated in two ways. First through the software and documentation of OpenAirInterface which is a leading community software and research tool in the field of mobile communications. Second, through issuing an article in a journal on computing for mobile communication.

As part of **Tasks 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4**, Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) are a major contribution and a building block in the overall COREnext architecture. BI finalized the development and integration of TEEs on its M³ platform, a microkernel system for a tile-based

hardware platform. The M³-based TEEs are implemented in a software simulator as well as on FPGA hardware. We presented a poster on our TEE notion at the EuroSys conference and submitted a full paper to the ACM International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems (ASPLOS) 2026. Furthermore, a security analysis of M³ was published in the Elsevier Journal of Systems Architecture (JSA) and an improved protocol for remote attestation was presented at the USENIX Annual Technical Conference (ATC) 2025 and is currently part of an ongoing standardization effort at IETF.

Task 4.3 additionally addresses Radio Frequency Fingerprinting, a device authentication method leveraging hardware-related impairments. The data from two identical SDR-based transmitters (USRP B205mini-i) connected to an SDR-based receiver (USRP B210) were collected by our colleagues from W5.1. Tests included a frequency band of 2.5 GHz at multiple high-gain settings. Our initial experiments with CNN model demonstrate near-perfect (>99%) accuracy in distinguishing two devices in closed-set scenario, even under varied training/test conditions and payloads. We also ran open-set tests with three devices: the anomaly-detection pipeline correctly flagged the unknown device in both the “easy” (B210 unknown) and “hard” (one B205 unknown) cases. These methods are also being evaluated in a 5G end-to-end link simulator, facilitating future integration into complex communication systems. We further extended these studies by introducing external power amplifiers (PAs) to the SDRs. This setup, influenced by varying supply voltages and non-linear behaviours, provides more challenging conditions. While differentiating completely distinct SDRs remains straightforward, distinguishing the same SDR fitted with different external PAs is more difficult from the provided dataset and given experimental conditions. We also studied temperature drift: the classification accuracy drops for temperatures below 25-30°C when the model was trained on warmed-up data; we proposed a mitigation to deal with that. Finally, we trained on wired data and tested over-the-air (OTA): in shielded line-of-sight setup the model works well, and we are now increasing OTA complexity to find the failure point.

Task 4.4 additionally addressed the development of a Trust Manager component integrating a trust manager orchestrator, a trust evaluation function and ML grouping techniques among others. Edge IoT devices like drones and collaborative robots (cobots) interact with the Trust Manager Orchestrator to enable secure and efficient operations. After clustering these devices, each group of devices is evaluated using tailored trust metrics. The trust evaluation function calculates a trust index for each device, which is sent to the trust manager orchestrator to maintain an up-to-date trust profile. To optimise performance, computational tasks are offloaded based on each cluster’s capabilities—such as processing power, memory, and network strength. The orchestrator then uses the trust index and task requirements to select the most suitable input node, ensuring secure, efficient, and adaptive task execution across the network.

Risk Assessment

While isolation and disaggregation are expected to enhance the trustworthiness of networks, the overhead may be prohibitive. However, this risk did not materialize as overheads of our trustworthiness mechanisms were shown to be negligible. Additional risks like components not being finalized in time for validation have also not materialized.

3.5 WP5: Trustworthy Analogue Components

		2023				2024				2025			
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
T5.1	Trustworthy radio links through HW imperfections and localisation												
T5.2	Development of energy-efficient sub-THz components for ultra-high speed data interconnect												

D5.1
M6
D5.2
D5.3
M7

In WP5, the partners develop concepts, methods, and circuits to increase the trustworthiness of communication links. WP5 is connected to WP4 and WP6. WP5 ends with M33 (Q3 2025) of COREnext.

WP5 consists of two main tasks:

- Task 5.1: Trustworthy radio links through HW imperfections and localisation
- Task 5.2: Development of energy-efficient sub-THz components for ultra-high speed data interconnect

Monthly WP5 meetings and individual task level meetings have taken place online.

Concerning **Task 5.1**, the following activities are done:

- Further development (jointly with T6.1) of "HW-in-the-loop" hardware platforms
- Generation of numerous datasets to support WP4 and WP6 activities and concept development in WP5
- Continued work on concepts development for RF Fingerprinting for Physical Layer Security of RAN
- Exploration of architectures and main sources of signal-distortions in Base Stations and Fake Base Stations.
- Exploration of the impact of Over-The-Air transmission on ability to identify Fingerprinting.
- Definition of methods to model simulated or measured RF power amplifiers for later use in a system model.
- Capture/Delivery of IQ data from series of Base Station RF Power Amplifiers
- Exploration of architecture of User Equipment Receiver being capable of identifying Fingerprinting
- Integration of the link-level simulator for the HW-in-the-loop demonstrator in T6.1
- System modelling and algorithm development towards Robust (sub) THz beamforming against Eavesdropper Attacks
- Demonstrators shown at EuCNC 2025

Deliverable 5.2: Refined Concepts for Trustworthy Radio Links Through HW Imperfections and Localization summarizes all project outcomes from Task 5.1 and has been filed as foreseen in M33.

In **Task 5.2** the following work has been finalized successfully and results transferred to WP6:

- Measurements and characterization of two tape-outs of the H-band TX- and RX-IC in B12HFC technology. The second being an improved version of the first design from 2024.

- Design and fabrication of an embedded Wafer Level Package (eWLB) for H-Band TX respectively RX using B12HFC technology, where the RFIC to PMF transition is implemented in the form of antennas radiating into the fibre.
- Design of a suitable mechanical RFIC to PMF coupling for the eWLB device.
- Definition, specification, fabrication, characterization of AFSIW diplexer and waveguides for D-band and for H-band.
- Design, fabrication of BaseBand multi-channel Receiver IC to be used in the full link PFM demonstration at D-band.
- Design and assembly of PCB for this IC
- Several conference appearances: EuCNC, irrmw-THz, EuMW.

Task 5.2 has been an excellent example of close, fruitful research exchange and cooperation amongst the partners involved.

Deliverable 5.3: Design of sub-THz transceiver circuits, and H-band plastic waveguide describes and illustrates all project outcomes from Task 5.2. It has a slight delay during the editing phase and has been filed in M35.

3.6 WP6: Component Validation in Lab

	2023				2024				2025				
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
T6.1 Trustworthy radio link validation													
T6.2 M ³ platform lab showcase													
T6.3 Accelerated signal processing capabilities on a RISC-V platform													
T6.4 High data-rate fly-over interconnects using Sub-THz-over plastic waveguides showcase													

D6.1
M8

During the third year, WP6 activity focused on the following work package objectives:

- WPO6.1: Demonstrate results from WP4 and WP5 based on simulation and experimentation over different realistic scenarios
- WPO6.2: Validate results against use case requirements from WP2 and trustworthy disaggregated computing architectures defined in WP3

The WP6 team continued with monthly meetings in 2025, and the team size was constantly growing to phase over the results of WP2 to WP5, develop the demonstrators and progress to the validation of the respective demonstrators in the lab. WP6 team met twice in 2025, at the plenary meeting in Frankfurt/Oder and the EUCNC 25 in Poznan. WP6 supported the achievement of milestone 8 in month 36 with the conclusion of the lab validation and the successful delivery of D6.1: Lab validation results.

WP6 team prepared demonstrators and dissemination material for the exhibition at EUCNC, demonstration videos, as well as a slide set for the advisory board meeting and the final review.

Achieved Outcomes

WP6 progressed well in the tasks related to its four key innovations:

- Task 6.1: Trustworthy radio link validation,
- Task 6.2: M³ platform lab showcase,
- Task 6.3: Accelerated signal processing capabilities based on RISC-V platform, and
- Task 6.4: High data-rate interconnects using Sub-THz-over-plastic waveguides showcase.

In the third year WP6 focused on lab validation of those innovations, demonstrating prototypes and measuring their performance in realistic scenarios. The goal was to validate that each innovation can effectively improve security or efficiency (or both), and to ensure they meet the use-case requirements defined earlier in the project. By integrating simulation models with real hardware prototypes, the project team evaluated each solution's behaviour in practice, which provides confidence in their readiness for further development and potential deployment.

Research Methodology: Each innovation was validated through proof-of-concept lab experiments, combining simulation (to model complex scenarios) with hardware-in-the-loop testing and prototyping. The team built dedicated demonstrators for each key area, often integrating components from multiple partners. This methodology provides a high level of confidence in the results, bridging the gap between theoretical research (earlier project work) and practical real-world application.

Key Findings and Results: The lab validations confirmed the viability of all four innovation areas, yielding the following key results and conclusions:

- **Trustworthy Radio Link Validation:** The project demonstrated radio frequency fingerprinting (RFF) as a viable technique to authenticate devices and detect intrusions on wireless links. In a private 5G network testbed, a machine-learning based RFF system achieved over *95% accuracy* in identifying legitimate devices and detecting impostors. During live demonstrations, no impersonation attacks succeeded, unauthorized devices were reliably flagged as “unknown,” proving the effectiveness of the approach. The validation included both user equipment and base station hardware. A notable insight was that legitimate base stations of the same make and model are hard to distinguish by their RF emissions (because high-quality transmitters leave little unique “fingerprint”). However, the team found that any rogue (fake) base station can be effectively identified by feeding a combination of signal features (frequency spectrum, IQ imbalance, amplification non-linearities) into an AI-based classifier. This detection works even better when using “*remodulated*” signals to cancel out channel effects. The implication is that RFF can augment traditional security: it adds a physical-layer defence that operates rapidly, which could offload higher-layer authentication protocols and reduce latency for device verification. The motivation for this work is clear: attacks like fake base stations or malicious devices are a growing threat, and these results show that *built-in radio hardware signatures* can help counter them in real time.
- **M³ platform lab showcase:** The M³ platform isolates critical workloads so that even if third-party or untrusted components are present, they cannot compromise other parts of the system. In the lab, M³ was prototyped on an FPGA and on a custom chip, and its performance was assessed using realistic workloads (e.g. signal processing tasks relevant to Open RAN

applications). Key result: The M^3 prototype provided strong security isolation with minimal performance overhead. Measurements showed that increased security did not prohibit low-latency operation. The overhead of the isolation mechanisms was negligible, and the system's response times remained comparable to state-of-the-art baseline solutions. This is a crucial finding because it demonstrates that security can be vastly improved *without* sacrificing the real-time performance required in telecom systems. The validation of M^3 also achieved a balance between security and efficiency, which was a major challenge identified in the project's architecture design. This success suggests that future base station designs can include hardware-enforced isolation to greatly enhance trustworthiness.

As a recommendation, the team highlights the need for continued research into processor architectures that cleanly separate security-critical and performance-critical functions, making it easier to verify the secure parts without impacting overall speed. They also recommend developing formal verification tools for the security components of processors, to mathematically ensure their trustworthiness.

- Accelerated signal processing capabilities based on RISC-V platform: to improve efficiency, COREnext investigated hardware acceleration for signal processing using open hardware. The team built a demonstration where a RISC-V processor-based platform (with a custom accelerator) was implemented in one of the computational kernels of a 5G RAN physical layer: the channel estimation and equalization. The lab validation successfully showed that the RISC-V accelerator could speed up the 5G network functions. The integration was done on an FPGA acting as a RISC-V system emulator, running real 5G baseband software with the hardware aids. This result proves the feasibility of using open RISC-V architecture to enhance telecom systems. Unfortunately, the integration initially planned into the open source OpenAirInterface 5G RAN of this computational kernel could not be performed within the term of the project. Priority was given to the integration of other computational kernels from an early period in the project term when the orientation of works on implementations was not known yet. But it should be performed in the scope of future projects and collaborations since it would provide a generic open interface available for computational kernel providers to plug their implementation in. Achieving this openness for every computational kernel would be significant: it means future projects could reuse these interfaces and components, reducing proprietary IP licensing costs and encouraging a more ecosystem-friendly approach to 5G/6G infrastructure. In summary, the accelerator showcase demonstrated improved processing efficiency for 5G tasks and set the stage for broader adoption of open hardware in the telecom industry. As a next step, the team suggests exploring advanced packaging technologies (like chiplets) and entirely new processor architectures to further push performance. Such technologies could allow multiple specialized chips to be combined for greater effect, supporting even more demanding real-time processing needs in the future
- High data-rate interconnects using Sub-THz-over-plastic waveguides showcase to address the ever-growing bandwidth demands within telecom and data-centre hardware, COREnext developed a short-range ultra-high-speed communication link using polymer microwave fibre (PMF) – essentially a plastic waveguide for sub-terahertz frequencies. In this lab validation, the consortium built an end-to-end demonstrator that included custom D-band and H-band

transceiver chipsets, an antenna-in-package (AiP) module, a plastic waveguide (fibre) for carrying the sub-THz signals, and standard baseband hardware (software-defined radio) for signal generation and reception. The system was tested over distances of a few centimetres up to a couple of meters, targeting data rates on the order of tens of gigabits per second. Key finding: The PMF-based link proved feasible and robust for high data rates in short-range scenarios, even under realistic conditions (e.g. including connector losses and alignment issues). The team evaluated its performance (throughput, error rates), power consumption, trustworthiness (since a physical wired link is inherently secure against remote eavesdropping), and cost factors. All partners involved were able to demonstrate their components working together, and the results were presented at a major conference (European Microwave Week 2025) to share insights with the broader community. This validation shows that low-cost plastic waveguides can deliver extremely high bandwidth for future computing systems, which is particularly interesting for connecting distributed modules in a base station or within data centres. A remaining challenge is to design equally advanced baseband and networking electronics that can fully utilize these links; for instance, handling >100 Gbps on a single fibre in real-time will require novel, efficient signal processing. The project recommends pursuing research into such energy-efficient, high-throughput baseband solutions to complement the PMF hardware, with the aim of eventually supporting over 100 Gbps communication on polymer fibres in practical applications.

Conclusions: This deliverable’s lab validations confirm that the COREnext innovations are both effective and attainable with current technology. Each prototype addressed a different facet of the overarching goal: making distributed computing architectures simultaneously more secure (trustworthy) and more efficient. The results are encouraging – for example, one can dramatically improve security at the radio and processor level without imposing unacceptable performance costs. Moreover, the successful demonstrations of open and novel hardware (like RISC-V accelerators and plastic waveguides) suggest that industry can adopt these approaches to push beyond the state-of-the-art in network capability and cost-effectiveness.

Risk Assessment

Within WP6 monthly meeting we have constantly monitored the progress of concepts for the validators and their realisation. No significant delays or other risks have materialized.

3.7 WP7: Computation-Communication Platform Integration Roadmap

WP7 consists of two main tasks, which have been running in parallel with the goal to create an integrated computing-communication-sensing platform roadmap, to be signed-off by all relevant

stakeholders in the field. An initial version of **D7.1: Computing-communication-sensing platform integration roadmap**, has been released at the end of 2024. This initial version consisted of contributions and views of the COREnext consortium only.

During year three, external experts have been asked to contribute to the document and to review the document in order to get it more broadly accepted. This has helped us to shape the final version of this Deliverable document.

Risk Assessment

No risks have occurred in WP7. The critical element was the collection of information and data from the external stakeholders, especially from the point of view of confidentiality versus publicly available information. As it has been clearly stated that the Deliverable is a public document, we have asked the experts for a final review before releasing the deliverable in order to make sure only public content is included.

3.8 WP8: Outreach, Exploitation and Collaboration

WP8 completed its planned activities in the final year of the project, consolidating COREnext’s communication, dissemination, exploitation, and stakeholder engagement efforts. Throughout year three, the work package made significant progress across the three tasks, ensuring that the project’s results and impact were effectively showcased to the research community, target stakeholders, and the broader public.

In year three, WP8 will submit **Deliverable 8.2: COREnext Impact Report Final** in December 2025, complying with all reporting obligations related to the work package for this period.

Apart from the specific WP8 contributions, this work package actively supported WP7 by attending monthly coordination meetings and contributing to the preparation of the **final CCS Platform Integration Roadmap (Deliverable 7.2)**. This collaboration ensured alignment between the technical results and the project’s communication and impact strategy. WP8 also contributed to other work packages by providing **branding and design support**, including visual materials, slide decks, videos, and graphical assets used for presentations and events.

WP8 held monthly meetings throughout the year (with an email follow-up in July) and maintained close collaboration among partners to guarantee effective coordination of outreach, exploitation, and collaboration actions. In year three, all partners contributed to WP8 activities by:

- Attending monthly WP8 meetings and providing inputs for reports and deliverables.
- Reviewing and validating communication and dissemination materials (website articles, videos, newsletters, and deliverable templates).
- Supporting online activity by sharing and engaging with social media posts.
- Contributing to the **COREnext Newsletters #9-12**, providing updates on technical achievements and event participation.
- Sharing information about COREnext-related events, demos, and scientific publications to feed communication content.
- Contributing to **stakeholder engagement activities** and providing updates on workshops and collaborations.
- Supporting the **collection of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** and exploitation data for the final impact report.
- Participating in **EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025** and **European Microwave Week 2025**, showcasing COREnext demos and technical results.
- Producing and reviewing video materials, including the **EuCNC recap video** and six **demo videos** highlighting the project's innovations.

Achieved Outcomes

WP8 made excellent progress in the third and final year, completing all communication, dissemination, and exploitation goals set in the Impact Master Plan.

During this period, WP8 ensured the project's achievements were broadly disseminated through digital platforms, events, and media, resulting in increased awareness and visibility of COREnext's innovations.

By the end of 2025:

- **Deliverable D8.2: COREnext Impact Report (Final)** was prepared for submission in December 2025, summarising three years of impact activities.
- The COREnext community reached over **1,800 followers** across social media and generated **more than 140,000 impressions**.
- Twelve newsletters, over 50 **awareness articles, one white paper, and 25 video productions** were published, along with continuous website and Zenodo updates.
- COREnext partners collectively produced over **38 scientific publications + 1 White Paper + 1 book chapter**, surpassing the project's KPIs.

Regarding **Task 8.1: Communication and Dissemination** outputs, in the final year, WP8 focused on consolidating the project's online visibility and communicating its key technical outcomes to a wide audience. Main highlights include:

- Publication of **COREnext Newsletters #9 – #12**, covering EuCNC participation, demo results, partner innovations, and final achievements.
- **Video production campaign** including the EuCNC recap video and six demonstration videos, later used for communication and review purposes.

- **SEO optimisation** of the COREnext website and YouTube channel to ensure long-term reach and visibility after project closure.
- Maintenance of the **COREnext website** with new content, interviews, and articles showcasing project impact.
- Thematic social media campaigns under **#COREnextDemos**, **#COREnextInnovations**, and **#COREnextGrandeFinale** to highlight achievements, innovations, and project milestones.
- Continued publication of scientific and awareness materials, ensuring open access compliance.

These efforts contributed to maximising COREnext's visibility and reinforcing its position within the European 6G research landscape.

For **Task 8.2: Innovation Management, Exploitation and Sustainability**, the focus in year three was to finalise exploitation and innovation management activities, ensuring the long-term sustainability of COREnext results. Key activities included:

- Collection and integration of **exploitation reports** and **KER descriptions** from all partners.
- Update of the **Innovation Management and Exploitation database**, consolidating all project innovations and their exploitation routes.
- Preparation of the final **Impact Report (D8.2)**, compiling the project's exploitation roadmap, KER maturity levels, and post-project pathways.
- Support to partners in defining exploitation strategies, including **commercial, collaborative, and research-based follow-ups**.
- Identification of opportunities for **technology transfer** and further R&D collaboration within national and EU programmes.

WP8 successfully demonstrated how COREnext's innovations contribute to **Objective 6**: developing a strategic roadmap for disaggregated communication-computing platforms involving European microelectronics and telecommunications players.

Finally, with regards to **Task 8.3: Stakeholder Collaboration Framework**, WP8 strengthened COREnext's network and visibility through clustering and event participation. Key achievements include:

- Active participation in **EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025** and **European Microwave Week 2025**, where COREnext partners presented demos, papers, and participated in workshops.
- Continued collaboration and contact with EU initiatives such as **HEXA-X-II**, **CENTRIC**, **CONFIDENTIAL6G**, and **TrialsNet**, exploring communication synergies.
- Engagement with **SNS JU** and **CHIPS JU** to align project messaging with European 6G objectives.
- Dissemination of project findings across relevant platforms and networks to reach a diverse audience of industry, academia, and policymakers.

Risk Assessment

No major risks were identified for WP8 during the third year.

The previously identified risk of **low engagement or delayed reporting** from partners remained under control, thanks to regular reminders, close follow-up, and active coordination by AUSTRALO. All deliverables were finalised on time, and the strong collaboration within the consortium ensured smooth completion of all WP8 objectives.

4 Advisory Board Report

The COREnext project consulted with the project's Advisory Board in an online meeting on November 5, 2025, reviewing the achieved project output by way of demonstrator presentations. The Advisory Board was present in full in its current composition. COREnext was represented by the core team and demonstrator task leads. Specifically, the board consists of:

- **Didier Belot**
Wireless Strategic Innovation Head in Technology Design Platform Division, ST Microelectronics
- **Nikos Kalogeropoulos**
Hellenic Telecommunications and Post Commission (EETT)
- **Dr. Sara Wilford**
Ethics expert, De Montfort University, Leicester, UK

The following subsections summarize the board's opinion on the achieved results and the project's impact.

4.1 Technical Remarks

For the **M³ demonstrator** showcasing the COREnext platform for hardware-based isolation, a question about the access control policy shown in the demonstrator was raised. It was made clear that the policy is configurable and re-configurable by the system operator at runtime.

For the **accelerated signal processing demonstrator** showcasing the improvements in processing efficiency, the board initiated a discussion on the suitability of the RISC-V vector extension in contrast to the custom solution chosen by Kalray. Pros and Cons were discussed and deficiencies of the current state of the RISC-V vector extension specification were pointed out, especially in comparison to other market solutions like Intel AVX.

For the **plastic mode fibre demonstrator** showcasing high-data-rate interconnects, a request was made to compare the energy usage of the plastic fibre against optical fibre in addition to copper-based wiring.

4.2 End User Perspective and Ethics Approach

We discussed how the project affects non-scientific people and end users and how our system design affects security, safety, and accuracy of information. We emphasised security as a top priority in standardisation discussions. Standardisation ensures new communication technologies are safe, reliable, and interoperable. By defining common security frameworks and technical requirements internationally, end users benefit from systems that protect their data, privacy, and connectivity without understanding the complexity.

We stressed the importance of making things secure and simple from the start. Security must be built on simplicity, and this mindset has been present since the project's inception. It was suggested to include this message in public outreach activities to communicate it to general stakeholders.

In addition, concerns of public education out wireless technology safety were mentioned and how to effectively reach people to understand the value and relevance of these technologies. We agreed that COREnext can only serve as an example here and that public outreach activities must broadly illustrate our current technical, ethical, and political standing.

4.3 Standardization and Differentiation

We discussed the strengths of Europe compared to other regions. We noted that Europe has a strong focus on trustworthiness and formal verification of hardware and software. This can be a privacy and reliability differentiator in the future as systems grow in complexity.

Regarding standardization, we discussed that Ericsson and Nokia are key players in standardisation and participate in industry alliances like 6G-AI and the German 6G initiative. This connects to the global context since our partners are in international networks, and telecommunications technology is a global industry. While it is difficult for an individual project like COREnext to have direct representation in standardisation forums, project ideas are funnelled through the participating organisations and certainly influence standardisation indirectly.